

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for Cathepsin B (UniProt ID: P07858) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence

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Abstract

Cathepsin B is a lysosomal cysteine protease involved in protein degradation and contributes to processes such as antigen processing, apoptosis, and tissue remodeling. Here we have characterized twenty-four Cathepsin B commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

P07858, *CTSB*, Cathepsin B, APP secretase, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

In humans, the cysteine cathepsin family consists of 11 members: CTSB, CTSC, CTSF, CTSH, CTSK, CTSL, CTSL2, CTSO, CTSS, CTSW, and CTSZ (1). Most cysteine cathepsins function as endopeptidases, breaking peptide bonds within their protein substrates. Cathepsin B, encoded by the *CTSB* gene, exhibits both aminopeptidase and carboxypeptidase activities. Cathepsin B is initially synthesized as a prepropeptide, which is cleaved into a 46 kDa pro-Cathepsin B. The pro-Cathepsin B is then further cleaved in the late endosome into a 33 kDa single-chain mature form. In the lysosome, the single-chain mature form is processed into a 24–27 kDa double heavy chain form and a 5 kDa light chain (2). Cathepsin B regulates autophagy (3, 4), and is involved in tumorigenesis (5-7) and immune responses (8-11). Mutations in the *CTSB* gene have been associated with cancer and neurodegenerative diseases (1, 12).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols and openly sharing the data (13-15). Here we evaluated the performance of twenty-four commercial antibodies for Cathepsin B western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence (also referred to as immunocytochemistry) following consensus protocols (16), enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of Cathepsin B properties and function. The platform for antibody characterization used to carry out this study was endorsed by a committee of industry and academic representatives. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (17).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells (16). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million “TPM” + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (13). The HAP1 expresses the *CTSB* transcript at 6.0, which is above the average range of cancer cells analyzed. A *CTSB* KO HAP1 cells were obtained from Horizon Discovery (Table 1).

To screen the twenty-four antibodies by western blot, WT and *CTSB* KO protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with all twenty-four Cathepsin B antibodies in parallel (Figure 1).

We then assessed the capability of all twenty-four antibodies to capture Cathepsin B from HAP1 protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2). The western blot screening (Figure 1) indicated whether each antibody recognized the pro-form or mature form of Cathepsin B. Accordingly, for the immunoblot step, we selected antibodies expected to detect the same Cathepsin B form recognized by the antibody used for immunoprecipitation. Two specific antibodies identified in Figure 1 were chosen: one recognizing the ~46 kDa pro-Cathepsin B and another detecting the ~33 kDa mature form. For antibodies that did not yield a detectable Cathepsin B signal in western blot (Figure 1), and for which the recognized form could not be determined, we referred to the manufacturer's datasheets for guidance.

For immunofluorescence, the twenty-four antibodies were screened using a mosaic strategy. First, HAP1 WT and *CTSB* KO cells were labelled with different fluorescent dyes in order to distinguish the two cell lines, and the Cathepsin B antibodies were evaluated. Both WT and KO lines imaged in the same field of view to reduce staining, imaging and image analysis bias (Figure 3). Quantification of immunofluorescence intensity in hundreds of WT and KO cells was performed for each antibody tested, and the images presented in Figure 3 are representative of this analysis (16).

In conclusion, we have screened twenty-four Cathepsin B commercial antibodies by western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human HAP1 WT and *CTSB* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 4 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications (13). High-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect Cathepsin B were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study Cathepsin B in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available Cathepsin B antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in Cathepsin B only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. Cathepsin B experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results (18). Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI:[10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (18). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

The cell lines, primary and secondary antibodies used in this study are listed in Table 1, 2, and 3, respectively. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) (19, 20). All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Antibody screening by western blot

HAP1 WT and *CTSB* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) Or Clarity Western ECL Substrate (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse, goat, and rat antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HAP1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x *g* for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

HAP1 WT and *CTSB* KO cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565). The nuclei were labelled with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. Number D3571) fluorescent stain. WT and KO cells were plated on a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (VWR, cat. number 100503-917) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Wisent, cat. number 311-010-CL). Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP151-500) for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum (Gibco, cat. number 16210-064) and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary Cathepsin B antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification (21). Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Dataset for the Cathepsin B antibody screening study <DOI>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC006132c001	CVCL_SK16	HAP1	<i>CTSB</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the Cathepsin B antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab125067**	1007912-1	AB_10972167	recombinant mono	EPR4323	rabbit	0.28	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab270998**	GR3402831-2	AB_3698245	recombinant mono	EPR24353-25	rabbit	0.46	Wb
Abcam	ab272408**	1091988-1	AB_3698247	recombinant mono	EPR22982-114	rabbit	1.010	other
Abcam	ab272409**	1046055-9	AB_3698248	recombinant mono	EPR22982-124	rabbit	1.032	other
Abcam	ab58802*	GR3447082-7	AB_940824	monoclonal	CA10	mouse	0.10	Wb
ABCD Antibodies	ABCD_AI867**	11/15/2024	AB_3076342	recombinant mono	C62A2	rabbit	0.004	NA
ABCD Antibodies	ABCD_AZ272**	11/15/2024	AB_3698277	recombinant mono	Darpin 8h6	rabbit	0.090	NA
ABCD Antibodies	ABCD_AZ319**	11/15/2024	AB_3698278	recombinant mono	DARPin 81	rabbit	0.013	NA
ABclonal	A23039**	6100003172	AB_3083445	recombinant mono	ARC59069	rabbit	0.600	Wb
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	AF953	FWN0222031	AB_355738	polyclonal	-	goat	0.20	Wb, IP, IF
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB2176*	HJQ0123111	AB_2086936	monoclonal	155714	mouse	0.500	IP
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB965*	JJY0222041	AB_2086935	monoclonal	173317	rat	0.500	Wb
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP1-19797	A4	AB_1641648	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP3-14882**	241145	AB_3598028	recombinant mono	S08-7H4	rabbit	0.000	Wb, IF
Cell Signaling Technology	31718**	1	AB_2687580	recombinant mono	D1C7Y	rabbit	0.05	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX134724	43537	AB_2887332	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.620	Wb
MilliporeSigma	ZRB1635**	NA	AB_3698368	recombinant mono	1G7	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Proteintech	12216-1-AP	00108078	AB_2086929	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.60	Wb, IF

Proteintech	31399-1-AP	00151932	AB_3669964	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.270	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	41-4800*	TB257970	AB_2533508	monoclonal	4B11	mouse	0.500	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-32651**	YE3913382A	AB_2809928	recombinant mono	JA11-02	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-35194**	YE3913563	AB_2849098	recombinant mono	ARC0395	rabbit	0.80	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-42576*	YE3913385B	AB_2911717	monoclonal	J11-A11	mouse	2.00	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-55403**	ZJ4493335A	AB_3667644	recombinant mono	3X1D6	rabbit	0.380	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Thermo Fisher Scientific	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	65-6120	AB_2533967	polyclonal	1.0	0.2
Thermo Fisher Scientific	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	62-6520	AB_2533947	polyclonal	1.5	0.75
Thermo Fisher Scientific	HRP-Goat Anti-Rat Antibody (H+L)	31470	AB_228356	polyclonal	0.8	0.4
Thermo Fisher Scientific	HRP-Donkey Anti-Goat Antibody (H+L)	A15999	AB_2534673	polyclonal	1.0	0.5
MilliporeSigma	Protein A, HRP conjugate	18-160	NA	polyclonal	1.0	2.0
Thermo Fisher Scientific	Alexa Fluor™ 555-Goat anti-Rabbit IgG (H+L)	A-21429	AB_2535850	polyclonal	2.0	0.5
Thermo Fisher Scientific	Alexa Fluor™ 555-Goat anti-Mouse IgG (H+L)	A-21424	AB_141780	polyclonal	2.0	0.5
Thermo Fisher Scientific	Alexa Fluor™ 555-Goat anti-Rat IgG (H+L)	A-21434	AB_2535855	polyclonal	2.0	0.5
Thermo Fisher Scientific	Alexa Fluor™ 555-Donkey Anti-Goat IgG (H+L)	A-21432	AB_2535853	polyclonal	2.0	0.5

Table 4: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Western blot			Immunoprecipitation			Immunofluorescence		
Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	WT/KO cell mosaic	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody
WT KO	WT KO	WT KO	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	WT	WT	WT
WT KO	WT KO	WT KO	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	KO	KO	KO
245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-	245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-	245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-	245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-	245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-	245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-			
Target protein detected (arrowhead)	Target protein detected (arrowhead) among others	Target protein not detected	Target protein captured in the IP	Target protein captured in the IP	Target protein not captured in the IP		Target protein detected (white staining)	Target protein not detected

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Figure 1: Cathepsin B antibody screening by western blot (1/2)

Figure 1: Cathepsin B antibody screening by western blot (2/2)

A) pro-Cathepsin B
Wb: MA5-32651**

Figure 2: Cathepsin B antibody screening by immunoprecipitation (1/3)

A) pro-Cathepsin B
Wb: MA5-32651**

B) mature Cathepsin B
Wb: 31718**

Figure 2: Cathepsin B antibody screening by immunoprecipitation (2/3)

B) mature Cathepsin B
Wb: 31718**

Figure 2: Cathepsin B antibody screening by immunoprecipitation (3/3)

Figure 3: Cathepsin B antibody screening by immunofluorescence (1/2)

Figure 3: Cathepsin B antibody screening by immunofluorescence (2/2)

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: Cathepsin B antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of HAP1 WT and KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated Cathepsin B antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilution used: ab125067** at 1/1000, ab270998** at 1/100, ab272408** at 1/500, ab272409** at 1/500, ab58802* at 1/200, ABCD_AI867** at 1/4, ABCD_AZ272** at 1/100, ABCD_AZ319** at 1/100, A23039** at 1/500, AF953 at 1/500, MAB2176* at 1/500, MAB965* at 1/500, NBP1-19797 at 1/100, NBP3-14882** at 1/1000, 31718** at 1/300, GTX134724 at 1/100, ZRB1635** at 1/1000, 12216-1-AP at 1/1000, 31399-1-AP at 1/1000, 41-4800* at 1/500, MA5-32651** at 1/100, MA5-35194** at 1/100, MA5-42576* at 1/1000, MA5-55403** at 1/250. Predicted band size: 37.8 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: Cathepsin B antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 1 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated Cathepsin B antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the Cathepsin B antibody **A)** MA5-32651** used at 1/500 or **B)** 31718** used at 1/500. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 3: Cathepsin B antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

HAP1 WT and *CTSB* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio on coverslips. Cells were stained with the indicated Cathepsin B antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (WT), red (antibody staining) and far-red (KO) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. When an antibody was recommended for immunofluorescence by the supplier, we tested it at the recommended dilution. The rest of the antibodies were tested at 1 and 2 µg/ml, and the final concentration was selected based on the detection range of the microscope used and a quantitative analysis not shown here. Antibody dilutions used: ab125067** at 1/300, ab270998** at 1/500, ab272408** at 1/1000, ab272409** at 1/1000, ab58802* at 1/500, ABCD_AI867** at 1/10, ABCD_AZ272** at 1/50, ABCD_AZ319** at 1/10, A23039** at 1/600, AF953 at 1/200, MAB2176* at 1/500, MAB965* at 1/500, NBP1-19797 at 1/1000, NBP3-14882** at 1/1000, 31718** at 1/1500, GTX134724 at 1/800, 12216-1-AP at 1/600, 31399-1-AP at 1/300, 41-4800* at 1/500, MA5-32651** at 1/100, MA5-35194** at 1/800, MA5-42576* at 1/2000, MA5-55403** at 1/400. Bars = 10 µm. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.